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Identification of a novel mutation of rare CLN6 case and computation protein structure

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ABSTRACT: Neuronal ceroid lipofuscinoses (NCLs), also known as Batten disease, jointly account for the highest incidences of hereditary neurodegenerative disease in childhood. This disease is mainly presented by vision loss, ataxia, premature mortality in later stages, and epileptic seizures. NCLs are categorized into different types that rely on deficiencies in several genes. CLN6 is one of the identified NCLs, and a mutated gene affects a transmembrane protein embedded in the Endoplasmic Reticulum (RM). Here, we report two cases presenting clinical features of CLN6. A homozygous novel mutation NM_017882.2: Exon 7: c.268A>G (p.Asn90Asp) as well as another homozygous mutation in NM_017882.2: Exon 3: c.679G<A. Following the finding of novel mutation, the Sanger sequencing method was employed to confirm the outcome. Also, we performed a 3D structure prediction for the CLN6 protein. InterPro was taken advantage to assess the domains and function in mutated sites. Both mutations are located in the extracellular domain of the CLN6 protein.

Keywords: CLN6 gene; NCLs; 3D-structure protein prediction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Batten disease or Neuronal ceroid lipofuscinosis (NCLs) is considered an inherited neurodegenerative disease. NCLs are a subset of lysosomal storage disorders presented by clinical features: blindness, seizures, motor deterioration, loss of speech, decreased cognitive abilities, and premature mortality in early age [1, 2]. As mentioned, Batten disease can cause a lysosomal storage dysfunction due to the buildup of ceroid lipopigment in neurons and other types of cells [3]. The prevalence of these disease groups is approximately 1:10,000 and 1:12,500 [4]. The inheritance pattern of NCLs is an autosomal-recessive procedure, although there is an exception for the CLN4 gene that traces a dominant nature [5]. In addition, nearly thirteen genes for the related disability have been identified (Table 1). Based on genetic sub-types, studies illustrate that the age of onset could happen in different periods of life, such as infantile, late-infantile, adolescent, and adult [6].

CLN6 (ceroid lipofuscinosis, neuronal, 6; OMIM 601780) is one of the proteins that presence of mutations through its gene could lead to the development of a category of NCLs. Generally, it is a multipass membrane protein that resides in the endoplasmic reticulum [7]. The structure of CLN6 has been completely identified as an N-terminal cytoplasmic domain, seven putative transmembrane domains, and a luminal C-

terminus. However, the exact function of a given protein is not clear yet [8]. Studies prove that the CLN6 protein binds with another protein called CLN8 and makes a complex. The CLN6-CLN8 Complex engages with the lysosomal proteins through the ER and then converts them to the Golgi [9].

Table 1. NCL type based on associated genes.

Gene	Location	Inheritance	Type of NCL (Based on age of onset)	OMIM
CLN1	1p34.2	AR ¹	Infantile	600722
CLN2	11p15.4	AR	Late-infantile	607998
CLN3	16p12.1	AR	Juvenile	607042
CLN4	Xp22.2	AD ²	Adult	302910
CLN5	13q22.3	AR	Late-infantile	608102
CLN6	15q23	AR	Variant late-infantile	606725
CLN7	4q28.2	AR	Late-infantile	611124
CLN8	8p23.3	AR	Juvenile	607837
CLN10	1p15.5	AR	Late-infantile	116840
CLN11	17q21.31	AR	Adult-onset	138945
CLN13	11q13.2	AR	Adult-onset	603539

1: Autosomal recessive; 2: Autosomal dominant.

Through this study, we represent two Iranian families with unrelated NCL. Parents of both families (Family A and B) are relatives (parents are cousins). Different symptoms and clinical features were recorded for patients. Visual impairment, unbalanced walking, and no hearing ability are known as the main clinical features for families A and B. Also, cerebellar atrophy, mental retardation, and blindness are the first symptoms that appear in the patient from Family B. Parents in family A and B are carriers, and all sons are homozygous. Whereas Family B has a homozygous son who died for the de novo variant of CLN6.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Sample collecting and DNA extracting

Two Iranian families have been investigated through this study. Two generations of all the families were observed, and family A has two affected boys, an affected girl, and one unaffected daughter. Our study reveals that cousins of proband II-1 (Figure 1) are suffering from developmental delay and mental retardation. Also, all the parents are unaffected, and two generations consanguineous family. The clinical features and physical disabilities were examined and recorded according to their physicians' reports of their history background.

A 6-year-old boy from Family A was referred to the laboratory with blindness, cerebellar atrophy, and mental retardation. All other physical disabilities with the age of onset were recorded. A sixteen-year-old boy of Family B was diagnosed with visual and cognitive impairments and locomotion disorders, meanwhile of this study, two probands of these families were passed away.

Blood samples were obtained from cases (patients and parents) in the Genome laboratory, Gorgan, Iran. In order to examine the prenatal diagnosis of the fetus, amniotic fluid was removed from the uterus for amniocentesis (15 weeks). About 30 ml of amniotic fluid was collected, and amniocyte culture was performed in situ. The genomic DNA was isolated by Blood DNA Genomic extraction mini YektaTajhiz DNA kit (YektaTajhiz, Tehran, Iran) (Cat No: FABGK001).

Figure 1. Pedigrees of the reported Iranian families (Family A and B). Circles indicate females, and squares signify males. Also, a diamond is used as a symbol for the fetus, and the gender is not known yet.

2.2. Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) Amplification

The sequences of forward and reverse primers are listed in Table 2. The PCR mixture contained 2 μ l DNA sample, 1.6 μ l of Reverse and forward primers (0.8 μ l of each primer), 6.4 μ l PCR buffer, and 10 μ l AmpliTaq. The step of PCR cycle conditions was as follows: One cycle of pre-denaturation at 95°C for 5 min followed by 32 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 30 secs, annealing at 61°C for 30 secs, and extension at 72°C for 35 secs, with a final extension at 72°C for 10 min. The PCR products were subsequently analyzed by using 1.5% agarose gel electrophoresis. Exons 3 and 7 (Respectively, Family D and Family A) of the CLN6 gene were amplified by PCR and related primers designed by Vector NTI Version 11.5.3 [10].

Table 2. List of primers for Sanger sequencing confirmation.

	Primer	Sequence	Length
Family A (Exon 3)	Forward	GCCTTGACTGGAATTGCATCTG	22
	Reverse	GAGCAAGAGAAAGGGCGTGATG	22
Family B (Exon 7)	Forward	TTTACGGTTTCCCAAGCACAGC	22
	Reverse	GAGAAGGTCCAGCGATCACAGG	22

2.3. Variant Analysis

2.3.1. Whole-Exome Sequencing (WES)

Whole-Exome sequencing (WES) was performed on the DNA samples of patient members of the families. The individual's DNA was extracted from peripheral blood samples and fragments from the coding regions of all known human genes targeted for amplification and sequencing. Agilent SureSelect V7 was used for target enrichment, and the Illumine Novaseq sequencer was used for generating paired-end sequencing of 150bp for each sequence read. Reads from the sequence output were aligned to the human reference genome (GRCh37) using the Burrow-Wheeler Aligner (BWA). Variants to the reference were called using the Genomic Analysis Tool Kit (GATK). Read depth was 700bp for all the patients and their parents.

2.3.2. Sanger Sequencing

In order to confirm the result of WES, genomic DNA sequencing was set up for the novel candidate variants in CLN6. First, primers were designed using Vector NTI Version 11.5.3 [10]. PCR was used to amplify the indicated exons plus additional flanking intronic or other non-coding sequence. After cleaning the PCR products, cycle sequencing was carried out using the ABI Big Dye Terminator Version 3.0 kit. Products were

resolved by electrophoresis on an ABI 3130 capillary sequencer. Sequencing was performed separately in both the forward and reverse directions. Comparing sequences with reference gene sequences was done by taking advantage of CodonCode Aligner 10.0.2 (Figure 2) (Codoncode Crop., Dedham, MA, USA).

Figure 2. Confirmation sequences of probands in two families.

2.4. Bioinformatics Analysis of Protein Model

Since there is no empirical structure for the protein of CLN6 in databases. Therefore, an in-silico investigation was designed for this aim. The protein sequence was obtained from the NCBI website. As it is cited before, there is no template for comparison. Hence, we took advantage of tools based on template-free modeling. The wild-type and mutant protein three-dimensional structures were performed by the AlphaFold database (<https://alphafold.ebi.ac.uk/>) [11]. Also, for protein function prediction (motifs and domains), another web application called InterPro (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/interpro/>) was used [12]. This approach could be a recommendation to understand better the function of proteins.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Clinical Feature

3.1.1. Family A

A sixteen-year-old boy was admitted to our laboratory with sight and movement problems. It was believed the case might have metabolic diseases, but the results of genetic metabolic disorders were negative. It turned out that the symptoms appeared from the age of eight months. Over time, his eyesight has become poor, although he is not totally blind. On physical examination, he also benefits from a healthy skeleton, and he can sit without support. Furthermore, it is observed that he could walk, but he has an unusual walking pattern and unstable gait. He shows normal muscle tone and strength. A brain MRI scan indicated cerebral atrophy, in addition, brain lesions such as white spots were clearly obvious. Another dominant feature is about the developing learning issues, in this case, he has poor concentration and no sign of learning. He has a deficiency in speech generation, and just some words are uttered by him.

The family of the patient referred to our laboratory was investigated, and his family background revealed that the two cousins also have the same physical features. They both are macrocephaly with poor cognitive skills. Unfortunately, we could not access their blood samples during this study.

3.1.2. Family B

There are two affected children in the given family, one of them is a ten-year-old girl and a six-year-old boy. No problems were reported during the pregnancy, although the boy was given birth by cesarean section in the 38th week. All the newborn measurements were normal, including weight, height, and head circumference. After he reached 2 years and six months, Speech abnormalities became apparent in the form of stuttering. In the meanwhile, there was no evidence of abnormal growth and development. Locomotion problems became evident at the age of 4 years. This problem was associated with frequent tumbles and imbalances while walking. Also, Nyctophobia was the first abnormal behavior sign at the same age.

Brain MRI (Super Conductive MRI) revealed a CSF intensity extra-axial about 34*14*18 mm lesion at the Lt middle fossa anteriorly extending medially with mild effect on the Lt temporal lobe gyri next to it. The lesion is well-defined and homogenous hypo at T1 and hyper at T2 sequences and shall be R/O for possible arachnoid cyst. The cerebellar folias are mildly more prominent. Both cerebral hemispheres are normal otherwise.

3.2. Sequencing Results

Extracted DNA for sequence analysis results in recognizing different variants in two Iranian families. The homozygous uncertain significance variant c.679G>A (p.Glu227Lys) in exon 7 of the CLN6 gene for the proband II-1 of Family A was determined. Also, parents and other unaffected siblings were carriers for the related variant, as shown in Table 3. Sanger sequencing confirmed heterozygosity of NM_017882.2: Exon 3: c.679G<A mutation in the Family A. One variant of uncertain significance (VUS) in CLN6 was identified. This missense variant p.E227K in CLN6 (NM_017882.2: Exon 3: c.679G<A) was found in ClinVar (Variant 522701) with a classification of conflicting interpretations of pathogenicity.

Table 3. Variant analysis results for Family A and Family B members

Family	Gene	OMIM	MOI	Exon no.	Variant	Variant Classification
Family A	CLN6 (NM_017882.3)	Ceroid lipofuscinosis, neuronal, Kufs type, Adult onset	AR	7	Chr15:68500735C >T; c.679G>A (p.Glu227Lys)	VUS*
Family B	CLN6 (NM_017882.3)	lipofuscinosis, neuronal	AR	3	c.268A>G (p.Asn90Asp)	VUS

*Variant of Uncertain Significance.

For Family B, mutation confirmation for the CLN6 gene identified one variant of uncertain significance (VUS) defined as NM_017882.2: Exon 7: c.268A>G (p.Asn90Asp) of CLN6 gene. This substitution could change the amino acid sequence and protein features. The outcomes of the variant study for this family are shown in Table 3 below. Our proband was homozygous for ceroid lipofuscinosis neuronal, and according to genetic tests performed on the parents and siblings, we learned that all of them are carriers in this position, due to this result, the autosomal recessive pattern is confirmed. Through their third pregnancy, this family returned to the Genome laboratory of Gorgan for prenatal tests. Chorionic Villus Sampling (CVS) was performed, and the fetus was heterozygous. Also, the ultrasonic assay was normal.

Whole exome outcomes were confirmed by performing Sanger Sequencing. Detected variants suggest the putative disease-causing mutation and autosomal recessive inheritance pattern for Neuronal Ceroid Lipofuscinosis.

3.3. Bioinformatics Analysis of Protein Models

According to the American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics standards, the variants with insufficient scientific evidence to fulfill criteria using either of these sets (pathogenic or benign) or evidence for benign and pathogenic is conflicting are classified as uncertain significance (VUS). These mutations could change the amino acid sequence and protein features.

As it is monitored in the Predicted Aligned Error graph (PAE), from amino acid one to about 40, there is a loop, and the expected position error is calculated between 25 and 30 Ångströms. As a result, the structure prediction for the rest of the amino acids is highly acceptable (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Predicted structure of CLN6 protein by AlphaFold database. According to the PAE graph (Predicted Aligned Error), the model confidence for first about forty amino acids structure displays very low pLDDT (<50) (red region), consequently it could be observed as a loop structure. Additionally, at the position of 200 the scored residue is about 30 Å with low pLDDT ($70 > \text{pLDDT} > 50$) (yellow region). The rest of three-dimensional structure could be observed in light blue and blue color that means the model confidences are confident and very high respectively ($90 > \text{pLDDT} > 70$, $\text{pLDDT} > 90$).

Both mutated sequences were assessed for predicting domains and their roles in cells (InterPro). Outcomes suggested that the changed amino acids are located in a membrane region. The mutation site of p.Glu22the, the 7Lys variant, has a role as a bound protein in the extracellular region and is categorized as a Non-Cytoplasmic-Domain or transmembrane helix. Also, other mutated amino acid (p.Asn90Asp) located in the 90 position of protein structure is predicated with the TMhelix model (Figure 4).

4. DISCUSSION

Neuronal ceroid lipofuscinosis (NCL) is the common name for a group of neurodegenerative disorders known with autosomal recessively inherited pattern. It is reported that children are affected more, however, the age of onset may start at any time. Different mutations in the genes of soluble lysosomal and transmembrane proteins could cause NCLs in different aging ranges. Although the range of mutations varies, the clinical features are almost similar in diverse forms, ranging from speech and visual disturbances, seizures, ataxia, cerebellar atrophy, and progressive loss in cognitive and motor abilities [13]. Also, Kufs disease has been known as a rare case of CLN6 in adulthood with no loss of vision [14].

Figure 4. Secondary Structure and Domain Identification. A) p.Glu227Lys variant, the mutated position in the protein involves the region of a membrane-bound protein. This region is predicted to be located outside the membrane and is called the Non-Cytoplasmic domain. B) For the other variant (p.Asn90Asp), the same function is predicted nevertheless, the location is embedded in the membrane. C) As could be perceived in the Figure, the secondary structure at the 227 position is coil, and for the 90 position helix is predicted.

NCLs are known for almost 20% of child cerebellar atrophy cases, indeed Batten disease stands in the second place of neurodegenerative disorders worldwide [15]. This study reported a novel mutation NM_017882.3: Exon 3: c.268A>G and a rare case NM_017882.2 Exon 7: c.679G>A of CLN6 gene. These mutations are pathogenic variants with high-risk factors for Neuronal ceroid lipofuscinosis. As mentioned, these individuals are identified with VUS variants (Variants of Uncertain Significance), and genotype-phenotype correlation for the affected family members could provide strong evidence for reclassifying the variant from VUS to likely pathogenic.

There is only one natural animal model for studying mutation in CLN6 at present. This mouse model carries a frameshift mutation termed *CLN6^{nclf}* and encodes a temporary protein product [16]. This model is a prominent target for gene therapy projects. For the first time, Holthaus et al. highlighted that bipolar cells of photoreceptors are potential targets for gene therapy. During this project, the *CLN6^{nclf}* models' gene was edited with the Adeno Associated Virus or AAV2-derived 7m8 vector. Therefore, by editing the genome of photoreceptors bipolar cells, the role of photoreceptors could be preserved. Although the exact mechanism is not completely known, further studies are highly recommended [17].

In another study, by taking advantage of the same mice model, the AAV9 vector containing human CLN6 was transferred to neonatal mice by ICV injections. The given vector includes a ubiquitous promoter, and it is able to decline motor dysfunction, gliosis, and neurodegeneration symptoms. Generally, targeting the CLN6 gene by the AAV9 vector significantly improves the living conditions of the mutant mice, moreover, the lifespan of treated mice increased [18].

Author's contribution: FS conducted all the laboratory assay tests, including experimental setup, data collection, and interpretation. NGN conducted the bioinformatical tests and performed data analysis, providing insights and interpretations based on the results. NGN also contributed to the writing process, including reviewing, editing, and providing valuable input for the manuscript. NG appointed as the supervisor of laboratory assays. All authors read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Ethics Statement: All the tests were performed at the Genome laboratory of Gorgan, Iran. The study has been approved by the Research Ethics Committees of Iran (IR.USB.REC.1399.035). Also, families and participants provided their consent in written form for this study.

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